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THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE DISTANCE IN TEACHER-STUDENT INTERACTION

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Abstract: *This article is aimed at determining the communicative distance in the relations of the elementary school teacher with his students, and for this, the "Methodology of studying the communicative distance" was used. The research was conducted on the example of urban and rural school students, and a comparative analysis of the collected results was made.*

Key words: *Elementary school students, teacher, communicative gap, communicative zone in a group.*

Annotation: *The purpose of this article is to identify the communicative gap between the elementary school teacher and his students using the distance learning method. The study was conducted on the example of studying urban and rural schoolchildren and a comparative analysis of the results.*

Key words: *primary school students, teacher, communication interval, group communication zone.*

The feelings of primary school students are characterized by their greater stability, clarity, depth and strength, which differ from the feelings of preschool children, and are characterized by a more relaxed course. The general emotional tone of primary school students is dominated by cheerfulness, a mood of spiritual activity. In lessons

and games during breaks, they are cheerful and active. This state is considered the norm in the emotional life of primary school students. A child who comes to school for the first time enters a psychologically new system of relationships with those around him. He begins to feel that his life has changed radically, that he has new responsibilities, not only to go to school every day, but also to comply with the requirements of educational activities. The child also begins to realize that he occupies a special place in the system of human relations. His parents, relatives, and those around him treat him not as a young child, but as a separate person who has his own duties and responsibilities, who can earn respect based on the results of his activities. The fact that family members are interested in the child's educational activities and achievements, as well as controlling him, the new treatment and attitude towards him will help him fully feel the change in his social status, and will change his attitude towards himself. One of the important characteristics of primary school students is their sense of trust in the teacher, in which the teacher has a great opportunity to influence the student. The child sees the teacher as a person with intelligence, intelligence, sensitivity, and kindness. In the process of starting educational activities, the child's interactions with adults and peers begin to take on a new look. The main task of primary school educational activities is to teach students to "read", to acquire knowledge. In the mental development of primary school children, significant changes occur under the influence of education. These changes prepare them for the transition to adolescence, which is a responsible period of their lives. It is during this period that we will focus on analyzing the extent of the gap in the relationship between the primary school teacher and students. The proper organization of the relationship between the primary school teacher and his students paves the way for the child's entry into interpersonal relationships, as well as the "teacher-student" system. If the primary school images given to the teacher's image were preserved in a traditional and complete way at all stages of the continuous educational process, then there would be no unnecessary difficulties in solving some psychological problems encountered in education. However, as students move to higher grades, their relationships with their teachers

become more diverse due to various objective and subjective factors (due to the increase in the number of subjects taught and the provision of education by different categories of teachers), and the opportunities for comparison and selection increase. However, the positive educational impact provided in primary school continues to have an impact at some point in a child's life. Taking this into account, it is necessary to analyze the stage of teacher-student relationships in primary school.

When we analyzed the communicative distance between primary school teachers and their students, we were able to observe the uniqueness and mutual compatibility of the relationship between the teacher and the children. Students limited themselves to the answer that they try to approach their teachers as communicators - sincerely (0.80). Teachers, on the other hand, expressed the opinion that their students establish a trusting relationship with them (0.72). Both when the teacher's image was evaluated by students and in their relationships related to the communicative distance, children tried to treat the teacher with trust. In turn, the criterion that controls the objectivity of students' assessments is the teacher's methodological indicators. When we studied the personal qualities of teachers, their tendency to communicate, emotional stability had an average level, self-confidence, social maturity and assertiveness, and a tendency to independence were also average. We can say that the communicative range of teachers' relationships with their students was also assessed objectively. Teachers, unlike their students, reported that their results were in the "trustworthy" relationship range (0.69). The other side of the result was that teachers also perceived their students as recipients of their own (0.67). This shows that the communicative range of teachers' relationships with their students was in the same range as both communicators and recipients. This indicates that teachers had an objective approach to the methodology.

From these results, it became clear that the communicative range indicators of students' relationships with their teachers have a high positive correlation as communicators. It is natural for students to always feel a desire to establish relationships with their teachers and, in turn, expect love, encouragement, and support from them. Indeed, in primary grades, students often have the motivation to gain the

teacher's attention and to create a positive image for themselves, and students have a high need to be a recipient along with participating as a communicator ($r=0.665$; $p<0.01$). However, the fact that this situation is difficult to find among students in the entire class is confirmed by the lack of communication in the group's communicative zone.

Thus, the regulation of teacher-student relations in the primary grades and their exchange of information directly increases the students' learning by creating a communicative position of a receptive, submissive nature in the transmission and assimilation of information. Given that, according to the characteristics of the methodology, the change in the group indicator along the communicative zone (GKZO) provides information about the relationship between the teacher and students in the processes of transmitting and receiving information, and this interval reflects values in the range from - 0.5 to + 0.5, the “ + ” sign characterizes the mastery of the skill of transmitting information, and the “ - ” sign characterizes the tendency to receive.

The process of transmitting information in the individual communicative activity of the teacher and students affects them as subjects in communication with others by transmitting information. This, in turn, characterizes the tendency to receive it, the participation of the individual as an object of communication, in relation to the transmission of information. The emergence of “social perception” between teachers and students in classroom interactions allows us to maintain a stable psychological climate in the group during interaction and cooperation. In our results, regardless of urban and rural schools and educational levels (Table 3), we are surprised that none of them clearly demonstrated the skill of transmitting information. It is likely that the consequences of students becoming passive recipients of information in their interactions with teachers (students - 0.03 to 0.14) would not be good. Teachers, along with acquiring the skills of transmitting information, should also ensure the activity of students (between 0.24 and 0.36). We believe that in the interactions between primary school students and their teachers, although students are active in establishing

individual relationships with teachers on their personal issues, they have problems understanding each other in the educational process. Perhaps, we can clarify this aspect of the issue by referring to the results of studying the communicative abilities of teachers and their emotional, cognitive and behavioral aspects.

In conclusion, the assessment of the teacher's image is high at the initial stage of the primary school, and then, depending on the change in the level of education, it may decrease.

The indicators of "propensity to communicate" in the personal qualities of primary school teachers have the same level of results for both those with up to 10 years of work experience and those with more than 10 years of work experience. This indicates that they are ready to cooperate with students, attentive, and do not fall into states of extreme anger or joy (internal excitement, passion). However, this does not indicate that their "I" concept is negative, but rather is a consequence of insufficient ability to control their behavior and determination. They have their own position as individuals who strive to recognize universal human values and adhere to moral rules. The lack of full-fledged formation of responsibility in them may be a result of the influence of work related to family problems.

The communicative range of the primary school teacher's relationship with his students is in the range of "trust" and "sincere trust" at all stages of education, and although students present themselves to their teachers as communicators and recipients, they remain in the role of receivers of information in the process of their relationship, changing the communicative zone in the group. This gives the impression that students are participating in their relationship with their teachers as "objects".

It is necessary to ensure the moral development of students in the relationship between the primary school teacher and his students. It turned out that this is characteristic of some students.

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